

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Problems related to education in the school system are currently a priority issue in many countries, since the realization that education is an important factor in the development of the nation, an element that can “change the world for the better”, encourages the development of new strategies to improve the quality of training of future primary school teachers. Therefore, expectations for schools and teachers have become very high: society expects that they will be able to effectively solve increasingly complex issues related to education and training of young people, guaranteeing high learning outcomes and good results in education. The purpose of the article was to analyze the necessary competencies of the future primary school teacher and find ways to develop them in the conditions of updated education. The leading research methods are generally accepted scientific methods, such as analysis and synthesis, the classification method, as well as various methods of collecting information. In the course of the research, a characteristic was given to the concept of “competence”, as well as its characteristics; identified current trends in the educational process, which form a set of competencies necessary for a future primary school teacher; the conclusion was made about what competencies a modern teacher should have. It was determined that the primary school teacher should develop the ability to lead, interact with the educational environment, resolve conflicts and promote values among students throughout the didactic process in order to give primary school students training in skills and knowledge that will become essential in their future. The practical significance of the research is determined by the fact that the resulting characteristics of competencies can be used in training programs for future primary school teachers.*

Keywords: *professional skill, educator, modern trends, education, school curriculum.*

Introduction

It is known that the process of teaching/training is a complex and dynamic phenomenon, which is accompanied by a multitude of variables that allow determining the level of assimilation of material by students, ranging from factors that concern students themselves (cognitive abilities, motivation, attention), to understanding the family / social context, as well as the school context [1; 2]. Research in the field of education has always questioned the influence of these factors on the quality of education and their interrelationship, but the following can definitely be stated: the quality of teaching and the teacher is the school variable that most of all influences the results of students [3-5]. Thus, the improvement of the school system largely goes through a policy of competent intervention in relation to teachers, aimed at ensuring that competent and motivated specialists work in the school.

During 6 years of life, at the age of 6 to 12 years, a student receives primary education. This is a fundamental stage for holistic personality formation, at which it is necessary to work on teaching expression and understanding at the oral and written level, as well as on acquiring reading, calculating, cultural, creative skills, etc. This is also an important period for the personal, educational and social development of the student, based on the experience that can give an access to compulsory secondary education in the future [6; 7]. In order to fulfil this mission and for the growth of the student, the figure of the primary school teacher plays a huge role, since they are responsible not only for programming, teaching and evaluating various basic subjects (or specific, depending on the circumstances) that are common to all students, but also is someone who tries to convey knowledge based on values, norms of coexistence, individual or collective habits, the development of intellectual, emotional, social, critical abilities, etc. [8].

In order to fulfil the elementary goal of primary education, the teacher must collect a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that enable to stimulate the student's motivation and ensure their

optimal learning and development, namely, the competencies necessary for a primary school teacher. In this direction, both reforms of the education and vocational training systems are being implemented, as well as the promotion of the processes of initial teacher training and advanced training of teachers aimed at acquiring skills and experience [9].

Over the past few years, the school education system in Kazakhstan has been undergoing reforms, which is called updating the content of education, which was approved by the Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan No. 988 of December 27, 2019 [11]. The purpose of updating the educational program is to ensure that the knowledge and skills of schoolchildren correspond to modern realities, which are expressed in the rapid development of science and technology. The essence of the new education system is as follows: now the main emphasis in the search for approaches to obtaining and consolidating knowledge should be placed on the development of critical thinking of the student, teaching the student to compare and analyze facts. Thus, criteria-based assessment has now become the main approach to determining the performance of schoolchildren; the amount of academic load in the lower grades has been reduced by 2-3 hours, which became possible due to the improvement of curricula; new subjects have been introduced into the curriculum and are taught according to modern textbooks; now more attention is paid to teaching in different languages, training programs have been developed in English for some subjects (for example, chemistry, physics, biology), but at the moment this form of training is possible only for high school students, etc. Thus, it becomes clear that a modern teacher must meet the modern trends of education in Kazakhstan, and for this to have the necessary competencies.

Materials and Methods

A scientific method is a set of rules for conducting an experiment in order to obtain new knowledge or update and improve existing knowledge. These rules are necessary to free research from the subjectivity of researchers. Therefore, the knowledge obtained is considered scientific and reliable. Since the main goals of science are to analyze, explain, predict and interfere/influence in accordance with reality, such goals can only be achieved using the scientific method. The scientific method is a form of human activity aimed at cognition of empirical reality. As a general procedure of actions aimed at the production of scientific knowledge, the scientific method consists, firstly, in asking questions about reality, for this it is based on observations and existing theories; secondly, the scientific method consists in predicting solutions to the problems posed and comparing them with reality through observation, classification and analysis of facts. The scientific method is also called the problem-hypothetical method, since it is based on the formulation of problems, issues or questions about reality and on assumptions or possible solutions to the issues under study. In this study, generally accepted scientific methods were used, such as analysis and synthesis, which interact inextricably, as well as the classification method and various methods of collecting information.

Let's take a closer look at the methods of analysis, synthesis and classification. Analysis means dividing the whole into parts, and its counter-understanding means synthesis. Synthesis is the transformation (unification) of two or more elements (components) into a new unit. Analysis is defined as a procedure that dissolves an intellectual or substantial whole into its constituent parts. Synthesis is defined as the opposite procedure: the combination of individual elements or substances that form a single whole. Analysis and synthesis, as scientific methods, are usually interrelated and are used inextricably with each other; they complement each other. Each synthesis is based on the results of the previous analysis, and each analysis requires a subsequent synthesis to verify and correct the results. This method was used in the study of the competencies necessary for a future primary school teacher.

Classification processes are methods and criteria for dividing (classifying) objects or situations into classes, that is, for classification. This method is also known as a classifier. In a narrow sense, classification methods are used to classify objects in existing classes according to parameters or criteria that have been thought out in advance as a characteristic of each of the groups/components of the classification. In this study, the classification method was used to compile a list of competencies necessary for a primary school teacher. The material basis of the research was the works of scientists

from all over the world studying the problem of identifying the concept of “competence”, as well as establishing requirements for future primary school teachers [1-4; 9; 12; 13]. The study is also based on the Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated December 27, 2019 No. 988 “On Approval of the State Program for the Development of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020-2025” [11]. This normative legal act regulates the strategy for the development and modernization of the educational system of the Republic of Kazakhstan for the next five years, defines the goals and objectives, as well as ways to implement them in order to improve the quality of education in Kazakhstan, which contributes to improving the living standard of the population and ensuring the competitiveness of graduates of Kazakh universities in the world market.

Results and Discussion

Currently recognized for its educational, formative and cultural value, the teaching profession today faces an increase in the number of changes and high expectations for the formation of new generations to help them actively navigate in society. Due to the changing needs for development and global growth, as well as the corresponding changes affecting the education and training systems in different countries, the demand for teacher skills is expressed not only in the features of knowledge transfer, but also in the direction of end-to-end learning, which allows teachers to be able to respond to the characteristics of a complex, global and rapidly changing modern society [14; 15]. Called to be more and more “professional in the field of education and training”, a teacher is not just a performer in relation to the central authority that gives orders, or not just an employee who depends on the traditions and ideology of reproducing the status quo [16]. This is a person who seeks to improve his professional level through training and cultural growth, gaining experience that is intertwined with educational activities, with multidisciplinary planning, didactic research and continuous training. Thus, the teacher directs the selection of cultural and didactic models, organizes them taking into account specific planning and actions.

The teacher rethinks their role in a more global perspective of teaching, and this dimension flows into the acquisition of deeper organizational skills in the performance of school work, helping to outline educational professionalism, which is characterized by an accurate “reflexive” competence that makes them capable of “reflecting in the course of action”. Thus, the teacher becomes a researcher working in a context whose professionalism depends not on the categories previously fixed at the level of theory and technology, but on the ability to build a new theory in relation to a unique case: they are limited in the means to solve situations, the choice of which depends on a preliminary consensus on goals. They do not separate the goals from the means, but define them interactively, structuring the problem situation. The teacher does not separate thought from action, thinking about the problem until the solution is found, which they will later have to transform into action [17].

As a reflective professional, the teacher does not remain closed in the idea that the use of certain techniques is sufficient for teaching but faces situations of uncertainty in which the use of flexible and innovative methods is appropriate. The establishment of “reflexive” epistemology in the international panorama of research and educational practice made it possible to emphasize the importance of using disciplinary, methodological and pedagogical knowledge by adapting them to different situations, to build forms of practical effective responses to emerging problems of practice. As reflexive agents, teachers are not limited to using a repertoire of teaching methods, but are called upon to reflect on practice. In this sense, the teacher's personality is set up in an open and dynamic way and is no longer focused on a closed identity [18; 19].

A professional is not someone who, having knowledge, claims to apply it as a set of methods in accordance with pre-established standards of situations and actions, but someone who takes into account the characteristics of the situation in order to maintain a constant dialogue with the surrounding circumstances. As is the case with the training of each individual, the teacher's personality is a procedural dimension that occurs over time and is supported by the knowledge, skills, abilities acquired in the period between initial training and continuous training. Remembering the importance of continuing education, the main attention should be focused not only on the acquisition

and transfer of additional knowledge, but also on the acquisition of another form of competence that turns the teacher into a researcher.

Training, being another fundamental element of professional identity, activates the space for exercises and experiments on oneself, which is also useful for developing a willingness to constantly question existing knowledge, behaviour and accepted strategies. Thus, the teacher's personality is an evolutionary path that by its nature involves teachers in a continuous process of learning and development, according to which the initial motivations that led to professional choice can certainly be revised, analyzed in critical aspects, subjected to revision and further reflection.

The concept of “competence” (lat. *Competens* – appropriate, capable) means the terms of reference of any official or body; mastery of knowledge, experience in a certain field. The professional competence of a teacher is the personal capabilities of a teacher that makes it possible to independently and effectively implement the goals of the pedagogical process. Competence determines the level of professionalism of an individual, and its achievements occur due to obtaining the necessary competencies, which is the purpose of professional training of specialists. The concept of “key competencies” acts in this context as a “nodal” concept, since competence has an integrated character, namely: it combines professional knowledge, intellectual skills, abilities and methods of activity [20; 21].

Competencies are understood as a set of interrelated personal qualities (knowledge, skills, abilities, methods of activity) necessary for high-quality productive activity. Competence is defined as the possession of relevant competencies. Pedagogical competence is a system of scientific knowledge, intellectual and practical skills, personal qualities and abilities, in conditions of sufficient motivation and at a high level of professionalism of mental processes, it provides self-realization, self-preservation and self-improvement of the teacher's personality in the course of professional activity. The purpose of the formation of pedagogical competence is to ensure proper professional training of the graduate and their competitiveness in the market of educational services. The main objectives of the formation of the pedagogical competence of the future specialist of primary education are: to create conditions for the formation of the professional culture of the future specialist; to activate the formation of the key competencies of the future primary school teacher; to ensure the mastery of technologies of self-organization and self-actualization; to form the professional mobility of students; to organize methodological, didactic support for students; to form social activity based on personal qualities and social skills of the individual [7; 10].

The professional competence of a teacher is a combination of personal qualities, general culture and qualification knowledge, abilities, methodological skills, the harmonious integration of which in pedagogical activity gives the optimal result [16]. The internal factors of the teacher are also important: personal qualities, his general culture, managerial and organizational capabilities, and only then - qualification competence, which presupposes knowledge, abilities, and skills of the acquired speciality. Professional competence is the basic characteristic of a specialist; it includes both substantive (knowledge) and procedural (skill) components and has the main essential features, namely, mobility of knowledge, flexibility of professional activity methods and critical thinking. The main structural elements of pedagogical competence are theoretical pedagogical knowledge (provide for the content of psychological and pedagogical knowledge defined by the curriculum), practical skills, personal qualities of a teacher.

The professional competence of a teacher determines their pedagogical skills. The importance of pedagogical competence for pedagogical activity is determined by its functions, which include the following: pedagogical self-determination; pedagogical self-motivation; pedagogical self-learning and self-improvement; pedagogical self-realization; pedagogical self-prevention and self-rehabilitation. Taking into account these functions in the process of forming pedagogical competence will ensure meeting the goals and addressing the challenges of professional training of future specialists [6; 13]. Although teaching is an area of constant development, and teachers are professionals in the field of permanent pedagogical education, in order to acquire new competencies and be able to apply new methods that contribute to improving learning processes, it is possible to

establish a number of basic competencies for each primary school teacher; the consideration and characterization of each of them:

1. **Planning.** A competent teacher should be able to plan and organize training, that is, to put into practice all these skills, abilities and knowledge acquired during training for their optimal application. Owing to the good structure and organization of their work, as well as the management of the resources, materials, space and time available to them, the teacher will be able to correctly set goals and plan the educational process, which will allow them to monitor the student's progress during training and, if necessary, adjust the training plan for maximum efficiency.

2. **Communication.** Teaching in itself is an act of communication, for this reason, the ability to communicate is a fundamental skill for a teacher as a participant in society. The effectiveness of a teacher in the transfer of knowledge and values largely depends on the success of students' training and their subsequent educational development. This is a period in a student's life when progress in verbal, oral and written communication is very high, therefore a well-established dialogue with the teacher is an important level one competence. In this competence, not only the verbal communicative element but also the non-verbal (gestural or postural) component is very important when transmitting a message, as well as an accurate understanding of the features of communication with children of primary school age. In this regard, it is also important to be able to listen carefully to others, use appropriate vocabulary, without using negative terms, or pay special attention to accents, tone and volume.

3. **Social competence.** A primary school teacher should be able to properly interact with students, as well as with their families, classmates, etc. The social competence of a teacher combines their intellectual and emotional behaviour in an educational context with the aim of social integration of all its members. These include teacher's ability to solve problems, empathy, to be able to put themselves in the shoes of their students and understand their feelings, attitudes or behaviour, assertiveness in communicating from a positive point of view, or a balance between intimacy and authority that allows for an adequate, fair and respectful relationship between teacher and student and, thus, promote productive coexistence in the classroom.

4. **Cooperation.** The work of a teacher is primarily an individual matter since the teacher is independently responsible for preparing and teaching lessons, however, it is becoming increasingly important that cooperation and teamwork serve as educational feedback for the teacher and their professional environment. Promoting collaborative learning, coordinated action between teachers to apply or update pedagogical methods in a common way, or communicating with family members in special situations such as disruption in the learning process or student's high performance, improve and modernize the educational process.

5. **Educational competencies.** Finally, the cognitive and didactic abilities of the teacher are very important, this means that students can share all their knowledge of the curriculum. A primary school teacher should put into practice all the theory of their academic and professional training and knowledge, for example, such as computer science, which is especially important in the conditions of updated education. Also, the application of this knowledge in specific areas and subjects to be taught. The teacher should search, evaluate and integrate the available information with the sole purpose of educating students. While exercising this competence, they should be able to adequately convey information to the student using exercises, materials, learning resources and strategies.

Based on research in the field of pedagogy, an attempt was made to establish and characterize the competencies that teachers should develop in accordance with the training program. For example, F. Achtenhagen, F. Oser, U. Renold [22] associate the professional competencies of a teacher with those situations of teaching and training in which they have to intervene: "The connection between the development of competencies, on the one hand, and the field of teaching and training, on the other hand, is an old problem that addresses the central issue of teacher training". The development of teacher skills implies, for each of these situations, a diagnostic part, an action part and, finally, an assessment part. Thus, they emphasize that the development of professional pedagogical skills depends on knowledge. These authors, based on previous studies and projects, indicate that the

concept of professional competence of a teacher is conceptualized in four dimensions: personal competence or self-competence, which includes various aspects of professional personal development, such as cognition, emotions, motivation, metacognition or ethics; cognitive and substantive knowledge, which includes theoretical and analytical requirements, such as, for example, “application of concepts”; functional and didactic competence, which includes technical, practical and functional requirements, such as “use of tools, equipment and technical resources”; and social and communicative competence, which includes interpersonal requirements, for example, “to interact in the service of others and with others” [22]. When considering the professional competencies of a teacher trained within this framework, the required disciplinary knowledge should be theoretical and professional knowledge of the curriculum of primary education at this educational level.

P. Gómez [23] conducted an interesting study aimed at the competence of teachers. In Australia, work was carried out on an organizational chart of teachers' competencies in five dimensions: promoting student learning, evaluating the results of this training and compiling reports on them, participating in professional training, participating in the development of curricula and other initiatives aimed at achieving results and partnering with the school community. The scheme identifies two aspects related to the education of schoolchildren, and it also considers three aspects of the teacher's work as a member of the community. Finally, it is worth highlighting the thoughts of Claude Lessard, a Canadian expert on competencies, who points out only two aspects of the curriculum, which are important because they emphasize the complexity of the characteristics of competencies associated with specific academic disciplines [24].

In the case of professional teacher training, everyone easily understands the logic of this training: the future teacher must learn how to manage the class, which is one of the main competencies. As can be seen from the studies reviewed, the concept of teacher competence or competencies is formulated in various aspects and described with varying degrees of accuracy depending on the authors. By analyzing these contributions, which various researchers believed to contribute to the consideration of the problems of determining the competencies that a future primary school teacher should develop in order to systematize them from the point of view of the curriculum, it is possible to arrange each of the proposed schemes in accordance with the scheme of dimensions and levels proposed by L. Rico [25]. The set of competencies is approximately the same and similar to the competencies generally accepted in the curriculum, but different authors highlight different priorities in order to establish the levels by which they distribute their competencies.

As for the knowledge necessary for the future primary school teacher to develop and achieve the analyzed competencies, the following should be distinguished: the concept of the curriculum, formulated in its various dimensions and levels; tools for analyzing school subjects from a conceptual, cognitive, formative and social point of view; tools for developing, implementing and evaluating teaching and training activities. Thus, the student show is studying to become a teacher knows and uses the concepts and procedures of the school curriculum and other didactic knowledge about its teaching and studying, which makes it possible to conduct a didactic analysis of the studied topics in order to develop and justify educational activities.

Conclusions

Teacher training requires educational institutions preparing future primary school teachers to perform two types of main tasks: the first and inevitable consists of the need to form an understanding of the importance of education and the role of teachers in this process; the second, no less significant task is to identify professional skills that need to be developed in the process of teaching a profession, structuring initial training and determining various ways of pedagogical work in continuing education. In order to help overcome some of the shortcomings or limitations that have been generated by encyclopedic or behavioral approaches to teaching, it is extremely important that teacher training focuses on the development of professional skills, namely competencies. While it cannot be ignored that the development of competencies may bring with it new difficulties or problems, for the solution of which it will be necessary to create a space for critical reflection and new conceptual and methodological frameworks, however, one of the fundamental problems of teacher training will be

solved in this process: the correlation between teacher training and the requirements of a specific professional practice.

Professional competencies develop gradually as students acquire a set of knowledge; they develop in action, in specific circumstances and include various abilities for professional activity and, therefore, include the use of a scale of values that gives them meaning in each specific context. From this perspective, it can now be recognised that teaching skills are becoming a turning point for supporting and guiding educational processes and pedagogical practice. Therefore, research related to the determination of the necessary competencies of a modern teacher, not only of elementary grades but also at all stages of the educational process as a whole, is promising for study.

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